

J9.COM and FIBA To Bring Next-Level Basketball Experience

MIES, Switzerland — [J9.COM](https://www.j9.com), the world's premier online crypto betting platform, and FIBA, the International Basketball Federation, has recently signed a three-year global partnership until 2024 to bring global basketball events closer to fans through unique digital experiences. The partnership marks J9.COM as the 10th FIBA Global Partner and the first Asian online betting firm to partner with a global sports association.

J9.COM will play a significant role in providing innovative activations and promotions online and courtside to FIBA and fans worldwide. Notably, J9.COM will present the FIBA Basketball World Cup 2023 Trophy Tour, a global event that will bring the FIBA Basketball World Cup Trophy to cities across the globe.

Frank Leenders, FIBA Media & Marketing Services Director-General, said, "J9's addition to the Partner Family is a testament of their trust in the FIBA platform and the value it can provide towards the strategy and global ambition. Fan experience is also a crucial aspect of any FIBA event and, in particular, the FIBA world cups."

Vesper Tian, J9.COM Marketing Operations Manager, expressed the platform's gratitude and ambition in fulfilling their role as a FIBA Partner.

"J9.COM always has the ambition and vision, which is to become a leading online betting platform globally. Having over a million users on J9.COM, we are also a pioneer in the online betting service with cryptocurrency. With our creative products, professional team, and passion for sports, I believe that J9, in partnership with FIBA, will do well in taking our part in the better development and promotion of basketball and bringing more joy to the game to global fans," Tian said.

As FIBA's newest Global Partner, J9.COM will also use the platform to give back to the community by promoting basketball-related activities alongside the FIBA Foundation as part of the company's corporate social responsibility.

Aside from these projects, part of the agreement includes J9.COM having commercial rights on all FIBA competitions, including the FIBA Women's Basketball World Cup 2022, the FIBA Basketball World Cup 2023, and the men and women FIBA Continental Cups.

James Chen, Managing Director of J9.COM, expressed his confidence in supporting FIBA and providing fans with a better experience, saying, "With our innovative and digital ways, we will be able to help FIBA bring the charm and joy of basketball to more fans across the world."

For the next three years, FIBA fans can expect a world-class gaming experience that will take basketball to the next level. As a pioneer of online crypto betting, J9.COM will continue focusing on globalisation to connect with more sports fans worldwide and provide new ways to introduce sports.